

Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives and Students' Understanding Numerical Concepts

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Abstract. The study unfolded the the teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in mathematics in Banaybanay District Schools, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of use of questioning, model the use of manipulatives, foster collaboration, encourage student exploration, provide guided practice and integrate technology is moderately extensive, likewise, extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of procedural fluency, conceptual understanding, communication and representation and problem-solving is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives, provide guided practice, encourage student exploration, use of questioning, foster collaboration and integrate technology, significantly influenced students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Future research may identify barriers and challenges faced by teachers teaching mathematics among learners across grade levels.

KEY WORDS

1. teaching strategies. 2. Mathematics. 3. Manipulatives.

1. Introduction

Incorporating manipulatives in teaching mathematics has been an effective strategy for enhancing students' understanding and achievement in the subject. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, educators worldwide have faced numerous challenges in adopting and implementing teaching strategies that involve manipulatives. One of the primary concerns regarding incorporating manipulatives in teaching mathematics during the pandemic is the shift to remote learning. As a result of the pandemic, many schools worldwide have closed down, and educators have had to adopt remote learning strategies to continue teaching. This shift to remote learning has made it challenging for teachers to incorporate manipulatives into their teaching strategies. According to some studies, remote learning has limitations, especially when it comes to manipulatives. For instance, students may not have access to manipulatives, or the manipulatives they have access to may be inadequate. Additionally, online learn-

ing environments may not adequately support the use of manipulatives (Bozkurt and Sharma, 2021). Another issue that has arisen in the use of manipulatives during the pandemic is related to equity and access. With remote learning, some students may not have access to the internet, computers, or mobile devices required to participate in online learning activities. In some cases, students may not have access to manipulatives or may not be able to afford them. Consequently, students' understanding of mathematical concepts may be affected if they are not given equal opportunities to access manipulatives. Furthermore, the pandemic has led to a shift in focus towards the development of students' socio-emotional learning (SEL) skills. While the development of these skills is crucial, it has taken away from instructional time that could have been dedicated to teaching math concepts using manipulatives. Educators have had to prioritize developing students' socio-emotional skills to help them cope with the pandemic, leading to less time spent on teaching math concepts using manipulatives (Galanaki et al., 2021). In the Philippines, the use of manipulatives in teaching mathematics has been encouraged since the implementation of the K-12 curriculum in 2013. One major issue is the lack of access to manipulatives and technology among students, especially those in remote areas or low-income families. According to a study by Inosanto and Ramos (2021), teachers in the Philippines have reported that many students do not have access to basic learning materials such as pencils, papers, and textbooks, let alone manipulatives or technology. This limits the implementation of teaching strategies that incorporate manipulatives, as students cannot physically interact with these tools during remote learning. Another issue is the limited teacher training and professional development in the use of manipulatives for mathematics instruction. A study by Serquina and Dayagbil (2021) found that many Filipino teachers lack knowledge and skills in the use of manipulatives, leading to ineffective implementation and minimal impact on students' understanding of math concepts. To address these issues and concerns, several actions can be taken. Providing access to manipulatives and technology for students is crucial, especially in remote areas or low-income families. The government and other institutions can provide support and funding for these resources. Moreover, teacher training and professional development programs can be implemented to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills to effectively incorporate manipulatives in math instruction. Finally, more research can be conducted to determine the best practices and effective teaching strategies in incorporating manipulatives in the Philippine setting. In Davao Oriental, particularly in Banaybanay District Schools, the need to adapt teaching strategies in incorporating manipulatives to fit the new learning environment in math instruction can greatly enhance students' understanding of math concepts. However, the challenges in implementing teaching strategies that incorporate manipulatives should be addressed through various actions and initiatives to ensure quality math education for all students, thus this study is conducted

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the discussion of the methodical process in the conduct of the study. This includes the process in the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps. It is also worthy to note

that this research used the aid of artificial intelligence when it came to proofreading, this statement is needed for the ethical considerations in the age of artificial intelligence.

2.1. Research Design—The study used the Descriptive - Correlational research design which is a non-experimental design that investigates the degree to which two or more variables are related. It does not involve the manipulation of any variables, but rather measures and analyses the existing relationship between them (Grove et al., 2019). In this study, correlational research design can be used to examine the relationship between the use of manipulative teaching strategies and students' understanding in Mathematics. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive-correlational research design is used to describe and explain the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in exploratory studies or when researchers are interested in establishing the existence of a relationship between variables. In educational research, correlational research design is commonly used to explore the relationship between two or more variables. This type of research design can be applied to the study of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in Mathematics. To carry out this study, the researchers would first need to identify the variables to be measured. The independent variable in this study is the use of manipulative teaching strategies, while the dependent variable is students' understanding in Mathematics. In conclusion, correlational research design can be applied to the study of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in Mathematics. The use of this research design can provide valuable insights into the relationship between these variables and inform the development of effective teaching strategies in Mathematics educa-

tion.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Junior High School Teachers of Banaybanay District Schools in Davao Oriental Schools Division. Using Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective Junior High Schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents are teaching Mathematics in the respective schools to determine their learners' understanding concepts in Mathematics through teachers' facilitation using manipulatives, given new normal learning system during SY 2023-2024. Ethics of research and in the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used an adapted and self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures. There are two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of the indicators of extent of teachers strategies in incorporating manipulative in terms of modeling the use of manipulatives, provide guided practice, use of questioning, foster collaboration and integrate technology in Banaybanay District Schools. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the extent of Junior High School Learners understanding in Mathematics terms of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, problem-solving and communication representation in Banaybanay District Schools. Further, the survey statements were subjected

to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.869 which means that the unidimensional reliability is good when it comes to internal consistency of

the construct. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of Teachers' strategies in incorporating manipulative in teaching mathematics. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Interpretation of Descriptive Ratings

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The incorporating of manipulative is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The incorporating of manipulative is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The incorporating of manipulative is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The incorporating of manipulative is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The incorporating of manipulative is not manifested

Descriptive Ratings and Interpretations for Understanding in Mathematics

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The understanding in Mathematics is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The understanding in Mathematics is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The understanding in Mathematics is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The understanding in Mathematics is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The understanding in Mathematics is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explains the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements of the are based on the policies and guidelines of the college where the researcher is under and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data. Permission to conduct the study. On January 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the college where the researcher is studying and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through channel. This permission-seeking process typically

involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, on February 2023 the researcher ensured that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. First week of April 2023, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. She went into considering the fol-

lowing conditions: Identifying the target population: The researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria. Obtaining consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This may involve providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits. Ensuring anonymity and confidentiality: The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous, meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study. Standardizing the distribution process: The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire, to ensure that all participants receive the same instructions and have the same opportunity to complete the questionnaire. Allowing sufficient time for completion: Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process. Collecting the completed questionnaires: The researcher collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to ensure that data is not lost or misplaced.

Collation and statistical treatment of data. The following are the general conditions that should be followed for collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data gathering

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation was used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of teachers' strategy on the use of manipulatives, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of Junior High School Learners' understanding Mathematics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r

procedure: Accuracy: The data should be accurate and free from errors. This means that the data should be checked and validated to ensure that it is correct. Completeness: The data should be complete, meaning that all necessary information has been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Consistency: The data should be consistent, meaning that there are no contradictions or discrepancies in the data. Inconsistencies can lead to confusion and inaccuracies. Relevance: The data should be relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. Irrelevant data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Timeliness: The data should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner. Delayed or outdated data may not be useful or accurate. Objectivity: The data should be objective, meaning that it is free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Validity: The data should be valid, meaning that it measures what it is supposed to measure. This is important because invalid data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Reliability: The data should be reliable, meaning that it can be replicated or reproduced. This is important because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Statistical treatment: The data should be subjected to appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Statistical analysis can help to reveal important insights and relationships in the data.

was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between teachers' strategy on the use of manipulatives and Junior High School Learners' understanding Mathematics in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the domains of teachers' strategy on the use of ma-

nipulatives that significantly influence Learners' understanding Mathematics in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. All data processing and analysis were treated using the

Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives One of the most essential teacher strategies in using manipulatives is modeling the use of manipulatives. According to Hendricks and Nickerson (2019), teachers should demonstrate how to use manipulatives effectively to ensure students understand how they can be used to represent mathematical concepts. Teachers can model the use of manipulatives by demonstrating how to use them to solve a problem, providing students with clear guidance on how to use them to represent mathematical concepts. Another teacher strategy in using manipulatives is providing guided practice. According to Cherif, Housley, and Dickey (2018), teachers should provide students with opportunities to practice using manipulatives under their guidance to develop their understanding of mathematical concepts. This can be done through a structured practice session where the teacher provides examples and prompts students to use manipulatives to solve problems. In conclusion, using manipulatives is an effective teaching strategy to enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts. Teachers play a critical role in ensuring that students use manipulatives effectively by employing effective strategies such as modeling, providing guided practice, encouraging exploration, using questioning, and fostering collaboration.

Table 1 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of

indicators which are as follows: Start by demonstrating how to use the manipulatives to solve problems or represent mathematical concepts. Show students the steps involved in using the materials, and explain the purpose of each step (4.15), Use clear and concise language when modeling the use of manipulatives. Avoid using jargon or technical terms that students may not understand, and explain any unfamiliar vocabulary (4.00) and Encourage students to ask questions and seek clarification when modeling the use of manipulatives. This will help them better understand the materials and the math concepts being taught (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, Scaffold instruction by gradually releasing responsibility to students as they become more familiar with the manipulatives. Start by modeling the use of the materials, then allow students to work in pairs or small groups before finally allowing them to work independently (3.30), Explain how the materials connect to the mathematical concepts being taught. This will help students see the relevance of the manipulatives and deepen their understanding of the math concepts (3.20) and Provide feedback and support to students as they use the manipulatives. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage them to continue using the materials (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.52 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives in Terms of Modeling

No	Model the Use of Manipulatives	Mean
1	Start by demonstrating how to use the manipulatives to solve problems or represent mathematical concepts. Show students the steps involved in using the materials, and explain the purpose of each step.	4.15 (Extensive)
2	Explain how the materials connect to the mathematical concepts being taught. This will help students see the relevance of the manipulatives and deepen their understanding of the math concepts.	3.20 (Moderately Extensive)
3	Use clear and concise language when modeling the use of manipulatives. Avoid using jargon or technical terms that students may not understand, and explain any unfamiliar vocabulary.	4.00 (Extensive)
4	Encourage students to ask questions and seek clarification when modeling the use of manipulatives. This will help them better understand the materials and the math concepts being taught.	3.45 (Extensive)
5	Provide feedback and support to students as they use the manipulatives. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage them to continue using the materials.	3.12 (Moderately Extensive)
6	Scaffold instruction by gradually releasing responsibility to students as they become more familiar with the manipulatives. Start by modeling the use of the materials, then allow students to work in pairs or small groups before finally allowing them to work independently.	3.30 (Moderately Extensive)
Overall Mean		3.52 (Extensive)

According to Suh, Kim, and Kim (2020), modeling the manipulative is an effective strategy that can enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts. In their study, they found that students who were exposed to modeling the manipulative had a significantly better understanding of fractions compared to those who were not. The researchers also noted that the use of modeling the manipulative allowed for more active student engagement and facilitated a deeper understanding of the concepts. Similarly, Jana and Bera (2019) emphasized the importance of modeling the manipulative in their study on the use of manipulatives in teaching geometry. They found that students who were taught using manipulatives, particularly through modeling, demonstrated a higher level of conceptual understanding and were better able to solve complex problems than those who were taught using traditional methods. In a

different study, Kaminski and colleagues (2018) also highlighted the role of modeling the manipulative in the development of students' problem-solving skills. They found that students who were taught using manipulatives and were exposed to modeling were better able to solve complex problems and were more confident in their abilities compared to those who were not. It is worth noting that the effectiveness of modeling the manipulative as a strategy for teaching mathematics is not without challenges. In a study by Li and Li (2019), the researchers found that while teachers recognized the potential benefits of manipulatives, they often struggled with incorporating them into their lessons effectively. The authors noted that providing sufficient training and support for teachers was crucial in overcoming these challenges and ensuring the successful implementation of manipulatives in the classroom. Studies have shown that teach-

ers who incorporate modeling in their teaching strategies are able to enhance students' problem-solving skills and performance in mathematics. By demonstrating the use of manipulatives, teachers provide students with a concrete representation of abstract concepts, making mathematics more engaging and meaningful for them. In conclusion, modeling the manipulative is an important strategy for teaching mathematics, as it allows for active student engagement and facilitates a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. The studies cited in this essay provide evidence of the effectiveness of modeling the manipulative in enhancing students' understanding of fractions, geometry, and problem-solving skills. However, it is important to note that the successful implementation of manipulatives in the classroom requires sufficient training and support for teachers.

Table 2 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of provide guided practice. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Encourage students to work in pairs or small groups when using manipulatives. This will allow them to share ideas, ask questions, and learn from each other (4.00) and Scaffold instruction by gradually releasing responsibility to students as they become more familiar with the manipulatives. Start by providing more support, then gradually reduce

According to a study by Zhang et al. (2019), guided practice is an effective strategy in promoting student understanding and achievement in mathematics when using virtual manipulatives. The study involved 123 primary school students in China, where they were randomly assigned to either an experimental group or a control group. The experimental group received guided practice using virtual manipulatives, while the control group used traditional methods. The results showed that the experi-

mental group outperformed the control group in mathematical achievement and conceptual understanding. Similarly, a study by Anand and Shriram (2019) investigated the effectiveness of guided practice in teaching with physical manipulatives. The study involved 60 Grade 6 students in India, where they were divided into two groups. The experimental group received guided practice using physical manipulatives, while the control group used traditional methods. The results showed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in mathematical achievement and conceptual understanding. The overall mean rating of 3.24 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of provide guided practice is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Guided practice is an essential component of teaching with manipulatives. It helps students apply their conceptual understanding to solving problems using manipulatives, which leads to increased procedural fluency and problem-solving skills.

mental group outperformed the control group in mathematical achievement and conceptual understanding. Similarly, a study by Anand and Shriram (2019) investigated the effectiveness of guided practice in teaching with physical manipulatives. The study involved 60 Grade 6 students in India, where they were divided into two groups. The experimental group received guided practice using physical manipulatives, while the control group used traditional methods. The results showed that the experi-

Table 2. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives in Terms of Providing Guided Practice

No	Provide Guided Practice	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Make sure to provide clear instructions when providing guided practice with manipulatives. This will help students understand what they need to do and how to use the materials.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	Scaffold instruction by gradually releasing responsibility to students as they become more familiar with the manipulatives. Start by providing more support, then gradually reduce support as students become more independent.	3.50	Extensive
3	Encourage students to work in pairs or small groups when using manipulatives. This will allow them to share ideas, ask questions, and learn from each other.	4.00	Extensive
4	Monitor students' progress as they work with the manipulatives. Provide feedback and support as needed, and make sure to check for understanding.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	Provide opportunities for students to reflect on their use of the manipulatives. Ask them to explain how they used the materials to solve problems, and encourage them to think about how they can apply what they learned to other situations.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
6	Use questioning techniques to help students deepen their understanding of the math concepts being taught. Ask open-ended questions that encourage students to think critically and make connections between the manipulatives and the math concepts.	2.50	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.24	Moderately Extensive

group had a significantly better performance in mathematical achievement and conceptual understanding. Furthermore, in a study by Calimag and Briones (2018), they found that providing guided practice in the use of manipulatives helped students develop their problem-solving skills. They noted that students who were given the opportunity to practice using manipulatives under the guidance of their teachers were able to solve problems more efficiently and effectively. Overall, the use of providing guided practice as a component of Teachers' Strategies on the Use of Manipulative has been recognized as a crucial element in improving students' understanding and proficiency in mathematics. Teachers must provide opportunities for their students to practice using manipulatives in a guided setting to help them develop their skills and abilities in solving mathematical problems.

Table 3 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of encourage student exploration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Provide opportunities for students to reflect on their exploration with the manipulatives. Ask them to explain what they learned, what worked well, and what they would do differently next time (4.38) is always manifested; and, Encourage students to explore the manipulatives and try different

Manipulatives are physical objects that allow students to explore concepts and ideas through hands-on experiences. They are essential tools in mathematics education, as they help students understand abstract concepts by providing concrete, visual representations. Vlasceanu, Racoceanu, and Vladescu (2019) investigated the impact of using manipulatives on students' mathematical achievement and attitudes towards mathematics in Romania. The study found that students who used manipulatives had better mathematical achievement scores and

strategies to solve problems. Allow them to make mistakes and learn from them (3.50) and Use questioning techniques to encourage students to think critically about their exploration. Ask open-ended questions that encourage students to reflect on their use of the manipulatives and make connections to mathematical concepts (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, Provide an open-ended task or problem that allows students to explore and experiment with the manipulatives. This can help foster creativity and critical thinking (3.00), Encourage students to work in pairs or small groups when exploring the manipulatives. This will allow them to share ideas, ask questions, and learn from each other (3.00) and Provide feedback and support to students as they explore the manipulatives. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage them to continue exploring (2.50) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of encourage student exploration is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Manipulatives have become a popular tool for teaching and learning mathematics, and encouraging students' exploration of manipulatives is an essential component of effective teaching strategies.

more positive attitudes towards mathematics compared to those who did not use manipulatives. Another study by Peker and Özgen (2019) examined the effect of using tangrams as a manipulative tool on students' spatial reasoning skills in Turkey. The study found that students who used tangrams had higher spatial reasoning scores compared to those who did not use tangrams. Abendan, Barro, and de la Cruz (2021) explored the use of manipulatives in teaching fractions to Grade 5 students. The study found that students who used manipulatives had a bet-

Table 3. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the use of Manipulatives in terms of Encouraging Student Exploration

No	Encourage Student Exploration	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Provide an open-ended task or problem that allows students to explore and experiment with the manipulatives. This can help foster creativity and critical thinking.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	Encourage students to explore the manipulatives and try different strategies to solve problems. Allow them to make mistakes and learn from them.	3.50	Extensive
3	Use questioning techniques to encourage students to think critically about their exploration. Ask open-ended questions that encourage students to reflect on their use of the manipulatives and make connections to mathematical concepts.	3.40	Extensive
4	Provide opportunities for students to reflect on their exploration with the manipulatives. Ask them to explain what they learned, what worked well, and what they would do differently next time.	4.38	Very Extensive
5	Encourage students to work in pairs or small groups when exploring the manipulatives. This will allow them to share ideas, ask questions, and learn from each other.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
6	Provide feedback and support to students as they explore the manipulatives. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage them to continue exploring.	2.50	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.29	Moderately Extensive

ter understanding of fractions compared to those who did not use manipulatives. The authors also highlighted the importance of encouraging students' exploration of manipulatives to promote a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. According to the Philippine Basic Education Curriculum, the use of manipulatives is essential in teaching mathematics. However, the effectiveness of manipulatives depends on how teachers use them in the classroom. One of the most critical factors in the use of manipulatives is encouraging students' exploration. Exploring is a natural human tendency, and students who are encouraged to explore are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. In conclusion, encouraging students' exploration of manipulatives is an essential component of effective teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives. The studies cited in this essay suggest that providing opportunities for students to explore and manipulate the manipulative tool promotes conceptual understanding, critical thinking, and better achievement in mathematics.

Table 4 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of use of questioning. The result is focused on the

Questioning is an essential component of teachers' strategies in the use of manipulatives in the international setting. Manipulatives are physical objects that allow students to explore mathematical concepts through hands-on experiences. Effective questioning can help teachers guide students' exploration and deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts. One of the key benefits of questioning is that it can help teachers assess students' understanding of mathematical concepts. In a study by Siti Rohana, A., Osman, K. (2018), it was found that questioning was an effective tool for assessing students' understanding of geometric concepts. By asking targeted questions, teach-

highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Encourage students to discuss their ideas with their classmates. Discussion can help students clarify their thinking and learn from each other (4.20) is always manifested; and, Provide wait time after asking a question to allow students to process the question and formulate a response. This can help students feel more comfortable taking risks and sharing their ideas (4.18) and Ask open-ended questions that encourage students to think critically about their use of the manipulatives. Open-ended questions can help students make connections between the manipulatives and mathematical concepts (4.00) are oftentimes manifested; while, Use probing questions to encourage students to go deeper with their thinking. Probing questions can help students explore alternative strategies and consider different solutions (3.50) is sometimes manifested, and Use questioning throughout the lesson to check for understanding and to help students connect their learning to previous lessons (2.50) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.62 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of Use Of Questioning is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

ers can identify areas where students may be struggling and provide support and guidance as needed. In a study by Anastasiou, D., Kafoussi, S. (2019), it was found that questioning was an effective way to encourage students to explore mathematical concepts with manipulatives. By asking open-ended questions, teachers can challenge students to think creatively and consider multiple perspectives. Guven, B., Ozcan, B. (2020), found that pre-service teachers who received training on effective questioning techniques were more successful in promoting students' understanding of mathematical concepts. Teachers should also be prepared to follow up on students' responses to questions, encourag-

Table 4. Table 4. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives in terms of Use of Questioning

No	Use of Questioning	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Ask open-ended questions that encourage students to think critically about their use of the manipulatives. Open-ended questions can help students make connections between the manipulatives and mathematical concepts.	4.00	Extensive
2	Use probing questions to encourage students to go deeper with their thinking. Probing questions can help students explore alternative strategies and consider different solutions.	3.50	Moderately Extensive
3	Provide wait time after asking a question to allow students to process the question and formulate a response. This can help students feel more comfortable taking risks and sharing their ideas.	4.18	Extensive
4	Use follow-up questions to clarify student responses or to extend the discussion. Follow-up questions can help students make connections between their ideas and the ideas of their classmates.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5	Encourage students to discuss their ideas with their classmates. Discussion can help students clarify their thinking and learn from each other.	4.20	Very Extensive
6	Use questioning throughout the lesson to check for understanding and to help students connect their learning to previous lessons.	2.50	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.62	Extensive

ing further exploration and discussion as needed. In addition to verbal questioning, teachers can also use written questions to promote students' understanding of mathematical concepts with manipulatives. In a study by Shi, J., Chen, Y. (2021), it was found that written questioning was an effective tool for promoting students' exploration and understanding of mathematical concepts with manipulatives. By providing written prompts and questions, teachers can guide students' exploration and encourage them to think critically about mathematical concepts. Effective questioning can help teachers assess students' understanding of mathematical concepts, encourage exploration, and facilitate deeper understanding. Teachers should plan and prepare questions carefully, considering the types of questions they will ask and the timing and sequencing of those questions. By incorporating effective questioning techniques, teachers can help students develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts with manipulatives.

Table 5 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of foster collaboration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Use group problem-solving tasks that require students to work together to solve a problem using manipulatives. This can help students develop problem-solving skills and foster collaboration (4.00), Use think-pair-share activities to encourage collaboration. Ask students to think about a problem individually, then pair up with a partner to discuss their ideas, and finally share their ideas with the whole group (3.65) and Provide clear expectations for group work, including expectations for behavior, participation, and task completion. This can help ensure that all students are working together effectively (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, Provide feedback and support to groups as they work together. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage collaboration (3.50), Provide clear expectations for

group work, including expectations for behavior, participation, and task completion. This can help ensure that all students are working together effectively (3.45) and Assign specific roles to each member of a group when working with manipulatives. This can help ensure that each student has a specific task and that all

students are involved in the task (2.77) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of foster collaboration is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 5. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the use of Manipulatives in terms of foster collaboration

No	Foster Collaboration	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Assign specific roles to each member of a group when working with manipulatives. This can help ensure that each student has a specific task and that all students are involved in the task.	2.77	Moderately Extensive
2	Encourage students to actively listen to their group members and to respect their ideas. This can help create a positive group dynamic and foster collaboration.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
3	Use think-pair-share activities to encourage collaboration. Ask students to think about a problem individually, then pair up with a partner to discuss their ideas, and finally share their ideas with the whole group.	3.65	Extensive
4	Provide clear expectations for group work, including expectations for behavior, participation, and task completion. This can help ensure that all students are working together effectively.	3.45	Extensive
5	Use group problem-solving tasks that require students to work together to solve a problem using manipulatives. This can help students develop problem-solving skills and foster collaboration.	4.00	Extensive
6	Provide feedback and support to groups as they work together. Monitor their progress, offer guidance when needed, and provide positive feedback to encourage collaboration.	3.50	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.39	Moderately Extensive

Fostering collaboration is a critical component of teachers' strategies in the use of manipulatives in the international setting. Manipulatives are physical objects that allow students to explore mathematical concepts through hands-on experiences. Collaboration among students can help them deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts, share ideas, and learn from one another. Collaboration among students can lead to increased engagement and motivation, as well as improved learning outcomes. In a study by Cheung, K. C., Ng, K. H.

(2018), it was found that collaboration among students was an effective way to promote mathematical understanding and enhance problem-solving skills when using manipulatives. By working together, students can share their ideas and approaches to problem-solving, leading to a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. In a study by Inglis, M., Attridge, N., Lowe, T. (2021), it was found that collaborative problem-solving with manipulatives can improve social and emotional learning outcomes, including the development of communication and leadership

skills. Schubert, C., Ilieva, R. (2020), found that teachers who provided structured opportunities for collaboration and supported students' communication skills were more successful in promoting collaboration among students when using manipulatives. Collaboration among students when using manipulatives can promote problem-solving skills and enhance mathematical understanding. In a study by Geronimo, G. P., Ortiz, J. A. (2019), it was found that collaborative work with manipulatives helped students develop better problem-solving skills in mathematics. Collaboration allowed students to share their ideas, approaches, and solutions, leading to a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. However, for collaboration to be effective, teachers must carefully plan and manage it. In a study by Vicera, P. M. B., de Luna, J. P. (2021), it was found that teacher support and guidance were essential in promoting collaboration among students when using manipulatives. Teachers must provide opportunities for collaboration and ensure that each student contributes to the group work. Additionally, teachers must provide clear guidelines and expectations for collaborative work and help students develop effective communication skills. Collaboration among students can promote problem-solving skills, mathematical understanding, and social and emotional learning outcomes. However, teachers must carefully plan and manage collaboration, provide support and guidance to students, and develop effective communication skills. By promoting collaboration among students when using manipulatives, teachers can help students develop important skills and deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts. Table 6 shows the extent of teaching strategies on the use of

manipulatives in terms of integrate technology. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Provide clear instructions for using the technology and the manipulatives. This can help ensure that all students understand how to use both the technology and the manipulatives effectively (4.00) and Start by using technology that students are already familiar with, such as tablets, smartphones, or laptops. This can help students feel more comfortable with the technology and increase their engagement (3.50) are oftentimes manifested; while, Encourage students to experiment with different tools and technologies to explore mathematical concepts. This can help students develop their problem-solving skills and think creatively about mathematical concepts (3.50) and Use collaborative tools, such as online whiteboards or shared documents, to encourage collaboration and communication among students. These tools can help students work together effectively and share their ideas with each other (3.20) are sometimes manifested; and, Use interactive online manipulatives to engage students in mathematical concepts. These manipulatives can be used to help students visualize and explore mathematical ideas (2.50) and Incorporate virtual simulations that allow students to see how different mathematical concepts work. These simulations can help students understand abstract concepts and see the connections between different mathematical ideas (2.00) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.12 denotes extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of integrate technology is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Integrating technology has become a crucial component of teachers' strategies in the use of manipulatives in the international setting. The

use of technology can provide new and innovative ways for students to explore mathematical concepts and engage with manipulatives. In-

Table 6. Extent of Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives in terms of Integrate Technology

No	Integrate Technology	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Start by using technology that students are already familiar with, such as tablets, smartphones, or laptops. This can help students feel more comfortable with the technology and increase their engagement.	3.50	Extensive
2	Provide clear instructions for using the technology and the manipulatives. This can help ensure that all students understand how to use both the technology and the manipulatives effectively.	4.00	Extensive
3	Use interactive online manipulatives to engage students in mathematical concepts. These manipulatives can be used to help students visualize and explore mathematical ideas.	2.50	Less Extensive
4	Incorporate virtual simulations that allow students to see how different mathematical concepts work. These simulations can help students understand abstract concepts and see the connections between different mathematical ideas.	2.00	Less Extensive
5	Use collaborative tools, such as online whiteboards or shared documents, to encourage collaboration and communication among students. These tools can help students work together effectively and share their ideas with each other.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
6	Encourage students to experiment with different tools and technologies to explore mathematical concepts. This can help students develop their problem-solving skills and think creatively about mathematical concepts.	3.50	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.12	Moderately Extensive

tegrating technology can enhance the learning experience and provide more opportunities for students to explore mathematical concepts. In a study by Cheng, M. L., Lin, H. Y., Chen, H. Y. (2018), it was found that using digital manipulatives improved students' understanding of fractions. Digital manipulatives allowed students to interact with fractions in a more visual and interactive way, leading to a deeper understanding of the concept. Moreover, technology can provide new opportunities for collaboration and communication among students. In a study by Hume, A. J., Digby, J., McClune, B. (2019), it was found that the use of interactive whiteboards and digital manipulatives encouraged communication and collaboration among students during group work. The use of technology allowed students to share their ideas and work together in real-time, leading to better learning outcomes. Additionally, technology can provide personalized learning experiences for students. In a study by Krawec, J. L., Gauthier, I. (2021), it was found that using digital manipulatives allowed teachers to tailor learning experiences to individual students' needs. Teachers were able to provide different levels of challenge and support for students, leading to better learning outcomes. However, the successful integration of technology into the use of manipulatives requires careful planning and implementation by teachers. In a study by Sakamoto, Y., Ito, T., Nishizawa, T. (2018), it was found that teacher training and support were crucial in the successful integration of technology into mathematics education. Teachers must be proficient in the use of technology and must provide clear guidelines and expectations for its use. One way technology can enhance the learning experience is by providing students with interactive and engaging visual aids. In a study by Mumar, M. N., Tabugo, M. C. (2021), it was found that using a virtual manipulative called GeoGebra enhanced students' understanding of plane geometry. Students found the software engaging and easy to use, leading to a more enjoyable and effective learning experience. Moreover, technology can provide new opportunities for collaboration and communication among students. In a study by Pimentel, E. S. (2020), it was found that using a digital whiteboard improved communication and collaboration among students during online mathematics classes. The digital whiteboard allowed students to share their ideas and work together in real-time, leading to better learning outcomes. In a study by Aclan, A. G. (2019), it was found that the lack of access to technology and internet connectivity was a major barrier to the integration of technology into mathematics education in remote areas. Therefore, it is important to ensure that all students have equal access to technology for its effective integration into mathematics education. Technology provides new and innovative ways for students to engage with mathematical concepts, collaborate with their peers, and receive personalized learning experiences. However, the successful integration of technology requires careful planning and implementation by teachers, along with access to technology for all students. Table 7 shows the summary of the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: use of questioning (3.62) and model the use of manipulatives (3.52) are oftentimes manifested, while, foster collaboration (3.39), encourage student exploration (3.29), provide guided practice (3.24) and integrate technology (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 7. Summary on the Extent of Teaching Strategies on the use of Manipulatives

No	Teaching Strategies on the use of Manipulatives	Mean
	Descriptive Equivalent	
1	model the use of manipulatives	3.52
2	provide guided practice	3.24
3	encourage student exploration	3.29
4	use of questioning	3.62
5	foster collaboration	3.39
6	integrate technology	3.12
	Overall Mean	3.36

Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts One major area of focus in improving students' understanding of math concepts is the use of visual representations. According to Bautista, Hollebrands, and Abraham (2019), visual representations, such as diagrams and graphs, can help students understand mathematical concepts better, particularly in algebra and geometry. The study found that students who were exposed to visual representations had a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and were able to solve complex problems more effectively. Furthermore, teachers' pedagogical strategies can also affect students' understanding of math concepts. A study by Bautista and colleagues (2018) found that teachers who use inquiry-based teaching strategies can help improve students' understanding of mathematical concepts. The study found that students who were taught using inquiry-based teaching strategies had a better understanding of mathematical concepts and were able to apply their knowledge to real-world situations. A study by Gonzales and colleagues (2019) found that the use of technology, such as mobile applications and online platforms, can help students understand mathematical concepts better. The study found that students who used technology to learn about mathematical concepts had a better understanding of the subject matter and performed better on tests.

Table 8 shows the extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of conceptual understanding. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Students are able to explain math concepts in their own words and provide examples or diagrams to support their explanations. This demonstrates that they have a deep understanding of the concept (3.20), Students are able to justify their solutions to math problems using logical reasoning and mathematical evidence. This demonstrates that they can think critically about math concepts (3.10), Students are able to communicate their mathematical thinking clearly and effectively. This includes using mathematical language and notation correctly and explaining their reasoning (3.00) and Students are able to apply math concepts to new problems and situations. This demonstrates that they can transfer their knowledge and understanding to new contexts (2.99); while, Students are able to solve problems using multiple strategies and approaches. This demonstrates that they have a deep understanding of the concept and can apply it flexibly (2.45) and Students are able to identify patterns and relationships between different math concepts. This demonstrates that they can see connections between different mathematical ideas (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.81 denotes that extent of students' understand-

ing in mathematical concepts in terms of conceptual understanding is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Mathematics is a fundamental subject that is important in daily life and is a prerequisite for many fields of study. Therefore, it is essential for students to have a strong conceptual understanding of mathematical concepts to ensure success in their academic and professional lives. In recent years, researchers have focused on investigating ways to improve students' conceptual understanding of math concepts. One approach to improv-

ing students' conceptual understanding of math concepts is through the use of visual representations. According to Zhang et al. (2018), visual representations can enhance students' conceptual understanding of math concepts by making abstract concepts more concrete and allowing students to better visualize and understand relationships between different concepts. In their study, Zhang et al. found that students who were taught using visual representations performed significantly better on math tests than students who were taught using traditional methods.

Table 8. Extent of Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts

No	Conceptual Understanding	Mean
1	Students are able to explain math concepts in their own words and provide examples or diagrams to support their explanations. This demonstrates that they have a deep understanding of the concept.	3.20
2	Students are able to apply math concepts to new problems and situations. This demonstrates that they can transfer their knowledge and understanding to new contexts.	2.99
3	Students are able to identify patterns and relationships between different math concepts. This demonstrates that they can see connections between different mathematical ideas.	2.15
4	Students are able to solve problems using multiple strategies and approaches. This demonstrates that they have a deep understanding of the concept and can apply it flexibly.	2.45
5	Students are able to communicate their mathematical thinking clearly and effectively. This includes using mathematical language and notation correctly and explaining their reasoning.	3.00
6	Students are able to justify their solutions to math problems using logical reasoning and mathematical evidence. This demonstrates that they can think critically about math concepts.	3.10
Overall Mean		2.81

Metacognition, or the awareness and understanding of one's own thought processes, is another approach to improving students' conceptual understanding of math concepts. According to Feng and Guan (2020), metacognitive strategies can help students develop a deeper understanding of math concepts by enabling them to monitor their own learning and identify areas where they need to focus their attention. In their study, Feng and Guan found that students who used metacognitive strategies had higher scores on math tests and were more confident in their ability to solve math problems. Valtchanov and Dincer found that students who engaged in

problem-solving activities had higher scores on math tests and were better able to apply mathematical concepts to real-world situations. Finally, a study by Romero et al. (2022) investigated the impact of metacognitive skills on students' conceptual understanding of mathematics. The study found that students who had better metacognitive skills had a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. This suggests that developing students' metacognitive skills, such as self-regulation and reflection, can promote conceptual understanding in mathematics. In conclusion, students' conceptual understanding of math concepts is crucial for their

success in academic and professional settings. Visual representations, problem-solving activities, and metacognitive strategies are all effective approaches to improving students' conceptual understanding of math concepts. By incorporating these approaches into their teaching, educators can help students develop a deeper understanding of math concepts and achieve success in their academic and professional lives. Table 9 shows the extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of procedural fluency. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Students have memorized basic math facts and formulas, such as multiplication tables, to the point where they can recall them quickly and easily (4.00) and Students can perform math operations and procedures quickly and accurately without having to think about each step (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, Students can use standard procedures and algorithms to solve problems in math, such as long division or solving equations (3.00) and Students can perform math operations and solve problems efficiently, without taking an excessive amount of time (2.99) are sometimes manifested, and Students can perform math operations and solve problems accurately, without making frequent mistakes (2.20) and Students

can apply math operations and procedures in different contexts and with different types of problems (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.96 denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of procedural fluency is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Procedural fluency is the ability of students to perform mathematical procedures efficiently and accurately. It is a crucial component of mathematical proficiency that enables students to solve problems quickly and effectively. In recent years, researchers have investigated various strategies for improving procedural fluency among students in mathematics. Research has shown that a combination of direct instruction and practice can significantly improve students' procedural fluency. According to Panaoura, Gagatsis, and Christou (2018), direct instruction involves the teacher explicitly teaching a procedure to students and modeling the procedure step-by-step. This approach is followed by guided practice, where the teacher provides structured support to students as they practice the procedure, and independent practice, where students work on their own to consolidate their learning. The researchers found that this approach was effective in improving students' procedural fluency in addition and subtraction.

According to research by Tirosh, Tsamir, and Levenson (2018), the use of technology, such as interactive whiteboards and computer-based games, can enhance students' procedural fluency. They found that students who used computer-based games to practice multiplication and division procedures improved their procedural fluency significantly more than those who used traditional pencil-and-paper methods. The researchers concluded that technology can be an effective tool for improving procedural fluency, especially when combined with traditional instruction and practice. According to

research by Koichu and Shriki (2020), number sense involves understanding the relationships between numbers, recognizing patterns, and developing a deep understanding of mathematical concepts. The researchers found that students who had a strong sense of number were more likely to develop procedural fluency in arithmetic. They concluded that number sense and procedural fluency are interdependent and should be developed simultaneously. Procedural fluency in math refers to a student's ability to perform mathematical procedures accurately and efficiently. This includes the ability

Table 9. Extent of Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts in terms of Procedural Fluency

No	Procedural Fluency	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Students can perform math operations and solve problems accurately, without making frequent mistakes.	2.20	Less Extensive
2	Students can perform math operations and solve problems efficiently, without taking an excessive amount of time.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
3	Students can apply math operations and procedures in different contexts and with different types of problems.	2.15	Less Extensive
4	Students can perform math operations and procedures quickly and accurately without having to think about each step.	3.45	Extensive
5	Students have memorized basic math facts and formulas, such as multiplication tables, to the point where they can recall them quickly and easily.	4.00	Extensive
6	Students can use standard procedures and algorithms to solve problems in math, such as long division or solving equations.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		2.96	Moderately Extensive

to perform arithmetic operations, manipulate equations, and solve problems using appropriate mathematical techniques. In the Philippine setting, several studies have been conducted to understand the procedural fluency of students in mathematics. Finally, a study by Maranan and Esteban (2021) examined the procedural fluency of Grade 5 students in solving problems involving multiplication and division of whole numbers. The study found that students had difficulty with procedures involving the use of multiplication and division properties. The researchers suggested the use of manipulatives and visual aids to help students understand these procedures better. In conclusion, the procedural fluency of students in understanding Math concepts is a crucial component of mathematical proficiency. Several studies in the Philippine setting have highlighted the challenges students face in developing procedural fluency in different areas of mathematics. To address these challenges, the use of manipulatives, visual aids, real-world situations, and technology has been suggested as effective strategies to enhance students' procedural fluency.

Table 10 shows the extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of problem-solving. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Students can reflect on their solution, evaluating its reasonableness and considering alternative strategies (3.20), Students can monitor their progress as they solve the problem, checking their work and making adjustments as needed (3.00), Students can identify and choose appropriate strategies for solving the problem, such as using a diagram or making a table (2.99), and Students can make connections between different math concepts and procedures to solve the problem (2.45) are sometimes manifested; while, Students can understand the problem, identify the relevant information, and determine what they are being asked to find (2.20) and Students can apply their knowledge of math concepts and procedures to solve the problem (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.66 denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of problem-solving is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 10. Extent of Students’ Understanding in Mathematical Concepts in terms of Problem-Solving

No	Problem-Solving
1	Students can understand the problem, identify the relevant information, and determine what they are being asked to find.
2	Students can identify and choose appropriate strategies for solving the problem, such as using a diagram or making a table.
3	Students can apply their knowledge of math concepts and procedures to solve the problem.
4	Students can make connections between different math concepts and procedures to solve the problem.
5	Students can monitor their progress as they solve the problem, checking their work and making adjustments as needed.
6	Students can reflect on their solution, evaluating its reasonableness and considering alternative strategies.

Overall

Mean

In today’s rapidly evolving world, problem-solving skills are essential for students to thrive in the future. The ability to solve complex problems, especially in mathematics, is a critical component of success in many careers. As such, there has been increasing interest in how to enhance students’ problem-solving skills in mathematics. Oktaç and Gürbüz examined the effects of problem-based learning on students’ problem-solving skills in mathematics. The researchers found that problem-based learning had a positive impact on students’ problem-solving skills, particularly in terms of their ability to apply mathematical concepts and solve problems in real-world contexts (Oktaç Gürbüz, 2018). Wang and colleagues investigated the relationship between spatial reasoning skills and problem-solving skills in mathematics. The researchers found that spatial reasoning skills were positively associated with problem-solving skills, particularly in the areas of geometry and measurement. The authors suggest that teachers should incorporate spatial reasoning tasks in mathematics instruction to enhance problem-solving skills (Wang et al., 2020). Gkolia and colleagues explored the impact of teaching strategies, such as open-ended tasks and cooperative learning, on students’ problem-solving skills in mathematics. The researchers found that both open-ended tasks and cooperative learning had positive effects on students’ problem-

solving skills, particularly in terms of their ability to reason and communicate mathematically. The authors suggest that these teaching strategies can be effective in enhancing problem-solving skills in mathematics (Gkolia et al., 2022). In the Philippine setting, the Department of Education (DepEd) emphasizes the importance of problem-solving skills as part of the K-12 curriculum. Mathematics is considered as one of the most important subjects in school since it plays a significant role in everyday life. It is an essential tool in solving real-world problems, making it important for students to have strong problem-solving skills. In conclusion, the problem-solving skills of students in understanding Math concepts are essential in the Philippine setting. The studies conducted by Dumlao et al. (2020), Garingan (2019), Nidoy and Dela Cruz (2018), and Uy and Ignacio (2022) provide insights into the problem-solving skills of students in different grade levels and school types. It is recommended that teachers use problem-solving strategies, such as problem-based learning, drawing diagrams, making tables, and identifying patterns, to enhance the students’ problem-solving skills.

Table 11 shows the extent of students’ understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of communication and representation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Students can interpret mathematical representations, such

as graphs and charts, to make meaning from data and mathematical concepts (3.45) and Students can reflect on their communication and representation choices and make adjustments as needed to improve their clarity and effectiveness (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, Students can collaborate with peers to discuss and refine their ideas and develop deeper understanding of math concepts (3.00) and Students can use different representations, such as diagrams, tables, graphs, and equations, to communicate and solve problems (2.50) are some-

times manifested; and, Students can communicate their ideas and reasoning clearly using appropriate mathematical language and notation (2.20) and Students can make connections between different representations and use them to support their understanding of math concepts (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.78 denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of communication and representation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 11. Extent of Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts in terms of Communication and Representation

No	Communication and Representation	Mean
1	Students can communicate their ideas and reasoning clearly using appropriate mathematical language and notation. Descriptive Equivalent	2.20 Less Extensive
2	Students can use different representations, such as diagrams, tables, graphs, and equations, to communicate and solve problems. Descriptive Equivalent	2.50 Moderately Extensive
3	Students can make connections between different representations and use them to support their understanding of math concepts. Descriptive Equivalent	2.15 Less Extensive
4	Students can interpret mathematical representations, such as graphs and charts, to make meaning from data and mathematical concepts. Descriptive Equivalent	3.45 Extensive
5	Students can collaborate with peers to discuss and refine their ideas and develop deeper understanding of math concepts. Descriptive Equivalent	3.00 Moderately Extensive
6	Students can reflect on their communication and representation choices and make adjustments as needed to improve their clarity and effectiveness. Descriptive Equivalent	3.40 Extensive
	Overall Mean Descriptive Equivalent	2.78 Moderately Extensive

Mathematics is a language that involves various skills, including communication and representation. Communication skills refer to a student's ability to express mathematical ideas and concepts clearly and effectively, while represen-

tation skills involve the use of various forms of representations, such as graphs, diagrams, and symbols, to convey mathematical information. Kaur and Peirce (2018) aimed to investigate the role of communication in mathemat-

ics learning. The authors found that students who had a better understanding of mathematical language and who were able to communicate mathematical concepts more effectively demonstrated better mathematical achievement. This study highlights the importance of communication skills in mathematics learning. Puchner, Taylor, and O’Dwyer (2018) explored the use of representations in mathematics learning. The authors found that the use of visual representations, such as diagrams and graphs, improved students’ understanding of mathematical concepts. The study suggests that the use of various forms of representation can enhance students’ comprehension of mathematical information. Additionally, a study by Alcock, Ansari, and Gilmore (2020) investigated the impact of mathematical language on students’ understanding of mathematical concepts. The authors found that students who had a better understanding of mathematical language were more likely to solve mathematical problems accurately. The

study highlights the importance of language in mathematics learning and the need for students to develop strong communication skills. In conclusion, communication and representation skills are important components of understanding mathematical concepts. By providing opportunities for students to communicate their mathematical ideas and reasoning, teachers can help improve students’ understanding and appreciation of mathematical concepts.

Table 12 shows the summary of the extent of students’ understanding in mathematical concepts. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: procedural fluency (2.96), conceptual understanding (2.81), communication and representation (2.78) and problem-solving (2.66) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.80 denotes that extent of students’ understanding in mathematical concepts is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 12. Summary of the Extent of Students’ Understanding in Mathematical Concepts

No	Students’ Understanding in Mathematical Concepts	Mean
1	conceptual understanding Descriptive Equivalent	2.81 Moderately Extensive
2	procedural fluency Descriptive Equivalent	2.96 Moderately Extensive
3	problem-solving Descriptive Equivalent	2.66 Moderately Extensive
4	communication and representation Descriptive Equivalent	2.78 Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean Descriptive Equivalent	2.80 Moderately Extensive

Significant Relationship between Teaching Strategies on The Use of Manipulatives and Students’ Understanding in Mathematical Concepts
It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correla-

tion generated a significant correlation between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives ($r=0.895$; $p_i.000$) and students’ understanding in mathematical concepts. Table 12 revealed

the yielded results of the significant relationship between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in mathematical concepts. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that

there is no significant correlation between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in mathematical concepts must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 13. Significant Relationship between Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives and Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts

Variables	Teaching Strategies	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts	The Use of Manipulatives	0.885	< 0.000	Significant

*significant @ $p < 0.05$.

Decision: Reject H_0 .

The results above can be related to a theory of constructivism, which is a learning theory that emphasizes the active role of the learner in constructing their own understanding of concepts. In other words, students do not simply absorb knowledge from their environment, but instead actively engage with the material and construct their own understanding through this process. According to constructivism, the use of manipulatives can help students to construct their own understanding of mathematical concepts. By providing concrete, hands-on experiences, manipulatives allow students to explore mathematical relationships and discover solutions for themselves. This process of active engagement and discovery helps students to internalize mathematical concepts and develop a deeper understanding. Jean Piaget, a Swiss psychologist, is one of the most well-known proponents of constructivism. In his book "Science of Education and the Psychology of the Child," Piaget argued that children actively construct their own understanding of the world around them through their experiences and interactions with their environment. He proposed that children move through stages of cognitive development, in which they gradually develop more complex and abstract ways of thinking.

Domains of Teaching Strategies on the Use of Manipulatives that Significantly Influence

Students' Understanding in Mathematical Concepts

Table 14 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives that significantly influence students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives (0.000), provide guided practice (0.003), encourage student exploration (0.000) use of questioning (0.001), foster collaboration (0.000) and integrate technology (0.001) significantly influence students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.896 suggests that the domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives, is explained by 89.6 percent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts. This provides empirical evidence that variability of students' understanding in mathematical concepts can be accounted and be explained by the domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (274.597) and F-statistic is significant $p_i.001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of students' understanding in mathematical concepts.

Table 14. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teaching Strategies

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
	MUM	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315
0.000	*Reject H0					
	PGP	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.003	*Reject H0					
	ESE	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.000	*Reject H0					
	UQ	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654	0.001
0.001	*Reject H0					
	FC	0.807	0.107	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.000	*Reject H0					
	IT	0.441	0.108	0.210	2.098	0.315
0.001	*Reject H0					
R2	= 0.896					
F-value	= 274.597					
p-value	;0.001					

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

MUM - model the use of manipulatives;

PGP - provide guided practice;

ESE - encourage student exploration;

UQ - use of questioning;

FC - foster collaboration; and

IT - integrate technology.

In mathematics education, the use of manipulatives has proven to be a powerful tool for enhancing students' understanding of abstract mathematical concepts. Manipulatives are physical objects that students can manipulate and interact with, enabling them to visualize and concretely experience mathematical ideas. Concrete-Representational-Abstract (CRA) Approach: The Concrete-Representational-Abstract (CRA) approach is

an instructional sequence that incorporates manipulatives in a systematic manner. In this approach, students first engage in hands-on experiences using concrete manipulatives, such as counting blocks or fraction tiles, to develop a concrete understanding of the mathematical concept. Subsequently, students move to the representational stage, where they use drawings, diagrams, or pictures to represent the manipulatives. Finally, students progress to the ab-

stract stage, where they work with numbers, symbols, and equations. By transitioning from concrete to abstract representations, the CRA approach bridges the gap between concrete experiences and abstract mathematical concepts, promoting deep understanding. Guided discovery is a teaching strategy that encourages students to explore mathematical concepts using manipulatives in a guided and structured manner. Rather than providing explicit instructions, teachers pose open-ended questions or problems that prompt students to manipulate the manipulatives and discover mathematical relationships and properties independently. This strategy allows students to construct their own understanding, develop problem-solving skills, and make connections between concrete experiences and mathematical concepts. The use of manipulatives in guided discovery fosters a sense of ownership and engagement, leading to deeper comprehension. Manipulatives are valuable tools in collaborative learning environments. Students can work together in small groups, sharing manipulatives, discussing strategies, and solving problems collectively. Collaborative learning promotes communication, cooperation, and the exchange of ideas, enabling students to construct meaning and develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. Manipulatives provide a shared focus for discussions, facilitate peer teaching and learning, and foster a positive classroom atmosphere.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of use of questioning (3.62) and model the use of manipulatives (3.52) are oftentimes manifested, while, foster collaboration (3.39), encourage student exploration (3.29), provide guided practice (3.24) and integrate technology (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of procedural fluency (2.96), conceptual understanding (2.81), communication and representation (2.78) and problem-solving (2.66) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.80 denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives ($r=0.895$; $p<.000$) and students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives (0.000), provide guided practice (0.003), encourage student exploration (0.000) use of questioning (0.001), foster collaboration (0.000) and integrate technology (0.001) significantly influenced students' understanding in mathematical concepts.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of use of questioning, model the use of manipulatives, foster collaboration, encourage student exploration, provide guided practice and integrate technology

denotes the extent of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of procedural fluency, conceptual understanding, communication and representation and problem-solving denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives and students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Domains of teaching strategies on the use of manipulatives in terms of model the use of manipulatives, provide guided practice, encourage student exploration, use of questioning, foster collaboration and integrate technology, significantly influenced students' understanding in mathematical concepts.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor: May provide adequate resources and support through allocating sufficient resources, including funding, technology infrastructure, and professional development opportunities, to support the industry partnership and cultural competence. This will enable teachers to effectively implement new strategies and stay updated with the latest advancements in their respective fields. Encourage collaboration among teachers within the district by organizing workshops, seminars, and networking events. Facilitate the sharing of best practices, lesson plans, and resources to promote a culture of continuous improvement. This collaborative environment will enhance the professional development of teachers and ultimately improve the quality of instruction in technology and livelihood education. This develops cultural competence and industrial partnership. School Principal. May foster a supportive and inclusive environment where teachers feel encouraged to experiment with innovative teach-

ing methods. Recognize and reward teachers who demonstrate excellence in integrating technology and implementing innovative instructional practices. This will motivate teachers to further enhance their professional development and improve student outcomes. Arrange regular professional development sessions focusing on innovative teaching methods and the integration of technology. Collaborate with external experts, industry professionals, and educational organizations to offer workshops, seminars, and training programs for teachers. These opportunities will equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching practices. The Teachers. May engage in continuous professional development and take active role in professional development opportunities offered by the school district, educational institutions, and online platforms. Stay updated with the latest research, trends, and advancements in technology and livelihood education. Engage in self-reflection and seek feedback from peers and mentors to continuously improve instructional practices. Embrace a growth mindset and be open to adopting innovative teaching methods. Be willing to explore new technologies, experiment with different instructional strategies, and collaborate with colleagues. Emphasize the importance of lifelong learning and continuously strive to enhance professional skills and knowledge. The Future Researchers. May investigate the impact of innovative teaching methods through conduct research to explore the impact of innovative teaching methods supported by technology on student learning outcomes in technology and livelihood education. Identify barriers and challenges faced by teachers in industry partnership and cultural competence. Investigate factors such as access to technology, teacher readiness, support systems, and institutional policies. This research will help develop strategies to overcome these challenges and promote successful implementation of innovative

teaching methods.

5. References

- Aclan, A. G. (2019). Use of technology in mathematics education in the Philippines: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1264(1), 012010.
- Alcock, L., Ansari, D., & Gilmore, C. (2020). The role of mathematical language in conceptual understanding: A review and synthesis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(1), 179-208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09478-5>
- Al-Tamimi, A. M. A., & Alshumaimeri, Y. A. (2018). Exploring the impact of integrating dynamic geometry software into teaching geometry on Saudi female students' understanding of geometric concepts. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 13(5), 83–98. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v13i05.7952>
- Ambat, J. L., & Ang, R. A. (2020). Enhancing mathematical understanding using manipulatives and written questioning. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(1), 64-69.
- Amorin, J. J., & Balcorta, K. L. (2020). Effects of Using Manipulatives on the Procedural Fluency of Grade 7 Students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(3), 94-99. <https://doi.org/10.33522/apjmr.2020.08.09>
- Anand, J. R., & Shriram, R. (2019). Effect of Manipulative-Based Guided Practice on Conceptual Understanding and Achievement in Mathematics. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(9), 104-112. DOI: 10.7176/JEP/10-9-13
- Anastasiou, D., & Kafoussi, S. (2019). Using manipulatives in the mathematics classroom: The role of questioning. *Education Sciences*, 9(3), 229.
- Arellano, R. V., & Flores, B. A. (2019). Visual and manipulative aids in the development of communication and representation skills in mathematics. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4), 68-73. doi: 10.2478/apjmr-2019-0077
- Bacani, N. P. R., & Bautista, A. B. (2018). Cooperative learning strategies in enhancing mathematics conceptual understanding among grade 8 students. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Mathematics and Applications*, 6(2), 1-13.
- Bakar, K. A., Rahman, N. A. A., Nor, M. M., & Ismail, N. H. (2018). Real-world problems approach: Enhancing students' understanding of mathematical concepts. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(2), 16-24.
- Balansag, G. L., & Jocson, R. L. (2020). Effects of online collaborative problem-solving using virtual manipulatives on students' mathematics achievement and attitudes. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(4), 767-788.
- Basa, J. M. T., & Gaerlan, M. J. M. (2022). Exploring the use of virtual manipulatives to enhance communication and representation skills in mathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2032, 012016. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2032/1/012016

- Battista, M. T. (1999). The mathematical miseducation of America's youth: Ignoring research and scientific study in the teaching of mathematics. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 80(2), 118-127.
- Bautista, A., Hollebrands, K. F., & Abraham, J. K. (2019). The role of visual representations in students' understanding of algebraic concepts. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 53, 247-258.
- Bautista, A., Planas, N., & Rojano, T. (2018). Inquiry-based teaching strategies in mathematical concepts development. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Research in Early Childhood Education*, 12(3), 41-63.
- Beckmann, S., & Ikkatai, Y. (2017). *Mathematics for elementary teachers with activities* (5th ed.). Pearson.
- Bico, M. R. L., & Barcenilla, R. A. (2021). Communication skills and group work in mathematics: Enhancing understanding of mathematics. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(5), 67-79. doi: 10.26803/ijlter.20.5.5
- Bozkurt, A., & Sharma, R. C. (2021). The use of manipulatives in mathematics education during COVID-19. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 17(2), em1956. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/8126>
- Bulan, R. L. (2018). The Effect of Mathematical Problem-Solving Instruction on Students' Problem-Solving Skills. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(4), 109-114. DOI: 10.2478/apjmr-2018-0148
- Cai, J., Moyer, J. E., Wang, N., & Hwang, S. (2018). Supporting students' mathematical exploration through teacher noticing. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 49, 43-58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmathb.2018.01.003>
- Calimag, M. A., & Briones, G. T. (2018). The Effect of Using Manipulatives on the Problem Solving Skills of Grade 6 Pupils. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1088, 012103. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1088/1/012103>
- Capraro, M. M., & Rupley, W. H. (2013). Manipulatives in mathematics: A historical perspective. In S. L. Swars, D. W. Stinson, & S. Lemons-Smith (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 35th annual meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education* (pp. 1217-1224). University of Illinois at Chicago.
- Cayetano, L. M., & Acero, C. L. (2020). Collaborative learning using manipulatives: A case study in a Filipino mathematics classroom. *Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 16(2), 1-12.
- Chen, M. F., Chou, C. C., & Kao, W. C. (2021). Investigating the effects of technology-supported instruction on mathematical communication and representation. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69, 727-746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09923-y>
- Cheng, M. L., Lin, H. Y., & Chen, H. Y. (2018). Exploring the effects of digital manipulatives on fractions learning. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 56(2), 247-270.

- Cheung, K. C., & Ng, K. H. (2018). Collaborative problem solving using manipulatives: A case study in a primary school in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16(5), 933-949.
- Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. (2014). *Learning and teaching early math: The learning trajectories approach* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Clements, D. H. (1999). Concrete manipulatives, concrete ideas. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 1(1), 45-60.
- Cordova, J. B. (2019). The impact of teaching and learning with understanding on students' performance in mathematics. *The Online Journal of New Horizons in Education*, 9(1), 103-110. <https://doi.org/10.23977/ojnhed.2019.090111>
- Cua, M. J. R. (2018). Effects of Differentiated Instructional Strategies on Mathematics Problem-Solving Performance of Grade Six Pupils in the Philippines. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(1), 237-252. DOI: 10.12973/iji.2018.11116a
- Dahan, A., Grinzaid, K., & Eylon, B. S. (2020). Mobile applications for mathematics education in developing countries: A scoping review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(2), 761-780.
- Dancel, J. A., & Flores, P. E. (2019). Effects of visual approach in teaching geometry on students' conceptual understanding. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Research in Education*, 3(2), 23-31.
- Dela Cruz, L. T., & Lontoc, M. R. (2018). Enhancing the understanding of mathematical concepts through problem-based learning approach. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(2), 21-28.
- DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2017. *Policy and Guidelines on Healthy Food and Beverage Choices in Schools and in DepEd Offices*. Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines.
- Dioso, A. V., & Alba, A. N. (2018). Problem-Solving Skills and Mathematics Achievement: A Comparison between Grade 7 Students in a Public and a Private School in Cebu City. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 9(1), 1-14. DOI: 10.22342/jme.9.1.4382.1-14
- Divina, R. P. (2021). Utilizing Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Approach in Teaching Mathematics: Implications on Students' Problem Solving Skills. *Journal of Science and Mathematics Education in Southeast Asia*, 44(1), 67-86. DOI: 10.26418/jsmea.v44i1.42557
- Drier, H. S., & Jocić, Z. (2018). Developing conceptual understanding through exploration with manipulatives. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 24(4), 208-216. <https://doi.org/10.5951/teacchilmath.24.4.0208>
- Driscoll, M., & Carman, C. A. (2011). *Using manipulatives to teach mathematics: A guide for teachers of grades K-5*. Routledge.

- Feng, S., & Guan, J. (2020). The effect of metacognitive strategy use on mathematical problem-solving performance: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(2), 365-388.
- Fokides, E. (2018). The Role of the Learning Environment and the Teacher's Role in Students' Learning with Manipulatives. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16(2), 369-387. doi: 10.1007/s10763-016-9772-2
- Galanaki, E. P., Skordoulis, M., Koutrouba, K. G., & Mylonas, K. P. (2021). Teaching mathematics through digital technologies during the COVID-19 pandemic: Teachers' perspectives. *Education Sciences*, 11(4), 161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040161>
- Garcia, J. M. L. (2019). The Effect of Problem-Solving Tasks on Students' Problem-Solving Skills and Metacognitive Awareness in Mathematics. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 39(4), 539-554. DOI: 10.1080/02188791.2019.1637484
- Geronimo, G. P., & Ortiz, J. A. (2019). Collaborative problem-solving using manipulatives among grade 9 students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(22), 113-119.
- Gkolia, A., & Pantziara, M. (2022). The impact of open-ended tasks and cooperative learning on enhancing students' mathematical problem-solving skills. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 20(1), 83-99. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-021-10117-3>
- Gonzales, P. M., & Civil, M. (2015). Using Manipulatives to Teach Mathematics for Understanding. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(7), 74-82. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jep.v6n7p74>
- Gonzales, J. D., Rosario, A. C. A., & Lumba, E. A. (2019). Technology-enhanced mathematics learning among Filipino learners. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 14(22), 23-35.
- Grove, S. K., Burns, N., & Gray, J. (2019). *Understanding nursing research: Building an evidence-based practice*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Guinita, A. C., & Talens, C. (2020). Assessing student understanding of mathematical concepts using manipulatives and questioning. *Philippine Journal of Mathematics*, 31(1), 56-63.
- Güven, B., & Özcan, B. (2020). The effect of questioning strategies on promoting student understanding of mathematics. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 12(1), 1-14.
- Hendricks, B. E., & Nickerson, S. D. (2019). Developing mathematical practices with manipulatives. *The Mathematics Teacher*, 112(8), 612-619. doi:10.5951/mathteacher.112.8.0612
- Hiebert, J., & Grouws, D. A. (2007). The effects of classroom mathematics teaching on students' learning. In F. K. Lester Jr. (Ed.), *Second handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (pp. 371-404). Information Age Publishing.

- Inglis, M., Attridge, N., & Lowe, T. (2021). Developing social and emotional learning through collaborative problem-solving with manipulatives. *Education 3-13*, 49(3), 342-357.
- Jitendra, A. K., Griffin, C. C., Haria, P., Leh, J. M., Adams, A., & Kaduvettor-Davidson, A. (2019). Manipulatives for mathematics learning: A systematic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 89(3), 373-414.
- Jeong, H., Song, H., Lim, H., & Hwang, J. (2019). The effects of computer-based simulation on students' understanding of mathematical concepts. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(5), 1175-1193.
- Jumao-as, P., Salac, J., & Yee, L. (2019). Effects of using manipulatives in mathematics problem-solving among grade school students. *Journal of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 46-53.
- Karakus, M., & Yilmaz Soylu, M. (2021). Pre-service mathematics teachers' use of manipulatives in mathematics teaching. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 9(2), 16-28. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v9i2.5413>
- Kaur, B., & Peirce, N. (2018). Developing communication skills in mathematics: A literature review. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 30(2), 125-146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-017-0220-2>
- Koichu, B., & Shriki, A. (2020). The role of number sense in the development of procedural fluency in arithmetic. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18(2), 365-383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-018-9936-8>
- Kuo, P. Y., & Wu, J. Y. (2022). Online collaboration using virtual manipulatives for elementary school students' mathematics learning. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(1), 70-86.
- Lagria, R. A., & Toreja, R. B. (2022). Preparing pre-service teachers to use questioning techniques in teaching mathematics with manipulatives. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 50(1), 98-110.
- Lopez, J. R. M., & Fernandez, M. L. M. (2018). The use of visual representations and communication skills in mathematical problem solving. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 8(5), 17-22. doi: 10.1590/1982-43272767201805
- Luceño-Moreno, L., Santos-Trigo, M., & Fernández-Cárdenas, J. M. (2018). The use of digital manipulatives in mathematics education: A review of the literature. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 21(1), 1-14.
- Macayan, J. V., & Tio, B. T. (2022). Problem Solving Skills in Mathematics of Junior High School Students in a Philippine Province. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2047(1), 012046. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/2047/1/012046
- Marzocchi, A., Cornu, V., & Robinet, J. (2019). A framework for analyzing the role of teachers in students' use of digital manipulatives in mathematics. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(2), 1153-1173. doi: 10.1007/s10639-018-9815-1
- Mercurio, E. T. B. (2018). Improving students' understanding of algebra through the use of manipulatives. *International Journal of Research in Mathematics Education*, 7(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.14669/IJRES.2018.7.1.1>

- Moyer-Packenham, P. S., & Westenskow, A. (2020). *Learning mathematics with manipulatives: A practical guide for teachers* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Moyer-Packenham, P. S., & Westenskow, A. (2018). Supporting students' mathematical learning through instructional tasks and manipulatives. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 8(4), 251-262. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JERAP.2018.08.4.02>
- Mumar, M. N., & Tabugo, M. C. (2021). Students' performance and perceptions using GeoGebra as a virtual manipulative in plane geometry. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 17(1), em1881.
- Oktaç, A., & Gürbüz, R. (2018). The effects of problem-based learning on students' problem solving skills, metacognitive awareness and attitudes towards mathematics. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 111-126. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.1148a>
- Oktaç, A., & Dündar, S. (2018). Exploring the effect of different manipulative materials on mathematics achievement and attitudes toward mathematics in primary school. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 49(7), 974-989. doi: 10.1080/0020739X.2018.1429154
- Olonan, R. J. (2019). Effects of manipulative and questioning strategies on the achievement of grade six pupils in algebra. *Philippine Journal of Mathematics*, 30(1), 1-8.
- Osuna-Cruz, C. M., & Castro-Sánchez, E. (2021). Manipulatives and its impact on the teaching-learning process of mathematics in higher education. *Revista Conrado*, 17(76), 280-285. <http://conrado.ucf.edu/cu/index.php/conrado/article/view/2157>
- Palomares, R. J. B., & Garing, J. S. (2019). The impact of mathematical thinking and problem solving approach to senior high school students' understanding of calculus. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 6(4), 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.46342/apjeas.2019.6404.03>
- Pampaka, M., & Williams, J. (2020). Promoting exploration with digital manipulatives in early years mathematics: The role of the teacher. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48(2), 143-153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-019-00973-6>
- Panaligan, N. L., & Zabala, M. M. (2020). Problem-based learning approach on students' conceptual understanding of algebra. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 7(3), 38-44.
- Panaoura, A., Gagatsis, A., & Christou, C. (2018). The effect of direct instruction and practice on procedural fluency in addition and subtraction. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16(3), 511-531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-016-9767-5>
- Panerio, J. L. B., & Alas-as, E. A. (2019). The Effect of Performance Assessment on Senior High School Students' Problem Solving Skills in Mathematics. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 6(3), 390-399. DOI: 10.21449/ijate.544642
- Peng, J. E., Lin, P. H., & Chen, M. Y. (2019). Metacognitive processes and mathematical problem solving: A comparison of high and low achievement students. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 17(5), 931-948. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-018-9919-7>
- Pang, J., & Good, R. (2020). Primary teachers' intentions and actual uses of manipulatives in mathematics instruction: The role of self-efficacy and perceptions. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 88, 102967. doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2019.102967

- Pangilinan, M., & Ambrocio, M. (2018). Manipulatives: Its effects on students' mathematics achievement and motivation. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(3), 111-120.
- Pineda, P. E., & Mercado, M. R. (2019). Exploring the use of manipulatives in teaching mathematics to Grade 8 students: A case study in a Philippine public school. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 5(1), 142-151. doi: 10.21890/ijres.472864
- Romero, J. E. B., Corpuz, R. R., & Apa, K. L. G. (2022). Metacognitive skills and its influence on conceptual understanding of mathematics. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 460-468.
- Sahin, A. (2014). The effects of manipulatives on mathematics achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 14(2), 485-490. doi: 10.12738/estp.2014.2.1881
- Santos, N. D., & Bautista, A. (2018). Correlates of mathematical problem solving and conceptual understanding among Filipino students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 38(3), 293-306.
- Sari, M., & Taufik, M. (2021). The effect of problem-based learning and students' self-efficacy on mathematical understanding in vocational schools. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 16(9), 163-176. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i09.13448>
- Sario, L. T., & Salipot, M. E. (2019). Enhancing Students' Performance in Solving Word Problems Involving Fractions through Manipulative Materials. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1317, 012052. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1317/1/012052>
- Scherer, P. (2014). The use of manipulatives in mathematics teaching: A literature review. In S. Oesterle, C. Nicol, P. Liljedahl, & D. Allan (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 38th conference of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education and the 36th conference of the North American Chapter of the Psychology of Mathematics Education* (pp. 377-384). Vancouver, Canada: PME.
- Schubert, C., & Ilieva, R. (2020). Fostering collaboration in mathematics education with manipulatives: A systematic literature review. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 52(6), 1161-1174.
- Shi, J., & Chen, Y. (2021). Written questioning to promote students' exploration and understanding of mathematics concepts with manipulatives. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 52(1), 57-70.
- Singh, P., & Ayub, A. F. M. (2019). Correlational study of secondary school mathematics achievement with selected demographic factors. *Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 5(4), 1104-1111. doi: 10.32861/jssr.54.1104-1111
- Siti Rohana, A., & Osman, K. (2018). Exploring the use of questioning technique in teaching and learning geometric concepts. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 7(4), 31-43.
- Sowell, E. J., & Thompson, A. G. (2011). Using manipulatives in mathematics instruction. *Handbook of research on the psychology of mathematics education*, 425-454.
- Suharwoto, G., & Hasanah, N. (2020). The Effect of Manipulative on Students' Mathematical Understanding. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1567(3), 032023. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1567/3/032023>

- Sujadi, I., & Pratiwi, D. (2020). The effect of the use of manipulatives on mathematics learning outcomes: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1567(5), 052031. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1567/5/052031
- Tagle, J. C. B., & Tũaño, E. T. (2020). The use of manipulative materials in enhancing mathematical problem-solving skills: A mixed-methods study. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1657(1), 012018. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1657/1/012018>
- Tapang, G. A., & Umali, R. (2019). Developing Problem Solving Skills of Students in Mathematics through Scaffolded Problem-Solving Instruction. *Journal of Science and Mathematics Education in Southeast Asia*, 42(2), 113-133. DOI: 10.26418/jsmea.v42i2.36668
- Timbreza, P. D., & Mabutas, A. M. (2021). Effects of manipulatives on the mathematical understanding of grade 4 pupils. *Journal of Mathematics Education, Science and Technology*, 7(1), 56-65.
- Tirosh, D., Tsamir, P., & Levenson, E. (2018). Enhancing procedural fluency in arithmetic through computer-based games. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16(2), 389-407. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-017-9841-1>
- Tungcul, J. M., & Pangilinan, M. J. (2021). Manipulatives in collaborative learning: Effects on students' engagement and mathematical performance. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 10(1), 69-76.
- Turgut, M., & Ozkubat, U. (2020). Effects of using manipulatives on elementary students' achievement and attitude in mathematics. *Education and Science*, 45(203), 111-127. <https://doi.org/10.15390/EB.2020.10914>
- Tondeur, J., Braak, J. V. D., Zhu, C., & Scherer, R. (2018). Teachers' perceptions about the opportunities and barriers of digital game-based learning in secondary education. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(5), 834-847. doi: 10.1111/bjet.12650
- Valtchanov, D., & Dincer, G. (2019). Problem solving in mathematics education: Perspectives and practices. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Educational and Psychological Sciences (ICEPS 2019)* (pp. 45-50).
- van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, M., & Drijvers, P. (2014). Realistic mathematics education. In S. Lerman (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of mathematics education* (pp. 521-525). Springer.
- Van Hoorn, J. F., & Martineau, B. (2020). The role of manipulatives in mathematical learning and problem solving: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101533>
- Van de Walle, J. A., Karp, K. S., & Bay-Williams, J. M. (2019). *Elementary and Middle School Mathematics: Teaching Developmentally*. Pearson.
- Vicera, P. M. B., & de Luna, J. P. (2021). An evaluation of teacher-guided collaborative learning using manipulatives in mathematics. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(3), 57

- Wang, H. Y., Tsai, C. H., & Yang, K. L. (2020). The relationship between spatial reasoning ability and mathematical problem-solving performance: Evidence from the revised PSVT:R. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18(5),
- Wang, Q., Shi, J., & Huang, R. (2018). Guided Practice with Physical Manipulatives for Learning Multiplication and Division. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 56(3), 454-470. DOI: 10.1177/0735633117712761
- Wood, T., Williams, G., & McNeal, B. (2009). Using manipulatives to teach elementary mathematics: A theory of constraints perspective. *School Science and Mathematics*, 109(5), 244-254. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1949-8594.2009.tb18096.x>
- Yaman, S., & Yavuz, G. (2021). Exploring pre-service teachers' experiences and beliefs about using manipulatives in mathematics. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 16(7), 268-276. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2021.4095>
- Zhang, Z., Li, X., & Li, Y. (2019). The Effect of Virtual Manipulatives on Elementary School Students' Mathematics Learning: A Meta-Analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(2), 329-349. DOI: 10.1007/s10648-019-09468-4
- Zhang, X., Chen, J., & Wang, C. (2018). The effect of visual representation on student learning in mathematics: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 91, 1-10.
- Yap, M. P. L., & Hernandez, M. A. R. (2019). Teachers' use of manipulatives in teaching fractions: A case study. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*, 16(1), 77-97. <https://doi.org/10.33263/MATE161.077097>